

Theoretical studies of refractivity of binary and ternary solutions

J. D. Pandey^{a*}, A. K. Shukla^b, N. K. Soni^a, K. K. Tiwari^a and Niti Pandey^c

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : jdpandey@rediffmail.com, drsoni_nk@rediffmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Shyama Prasad Mukherjee Government Degree College, Phaphamau, Allahabad, Uttar Pradesh, India

^cDepartment of Chemistry, Kamla Nehru Institute of Science, Sultanpur, Awadh University, Uttar Pradesh, India

Manuscript received 22 March 2007, revised 3 May 2007, accepted 10 May 2007

Abstract : The deviations in molar refraction, reduced free volume and refractive index have been calculated for eleven binary and six ternary solutions at 298.15 K. Sign and magnitude of these properties have been utilized to illustrate the molecular interactions occurring in the systems. Moreover, Lorentz-Lorenz, Gladstone-Dale, Wiener, Heller, Arago-Biot, Eykman and Oster relations have been used for theoretical prediction of refractive indices of all the solutions selected for the present study.

Keywords : Refractivity, binary solutions, ternary solutions, thermophysical properties.

Thermophysical properties¹ of a solution provide complementary information about the mixing process and interactions between their components. The study of thermodynamic properties of binary² and ternary³ solutions has gained much interest during recent years due to their industrial applications. The accurate prediction of refractive index is an interesting objective due to the increased interest in theoretical and empirical correlations⁴ of refractive index with other properties that are more difficult to measure directly. In literature, several correlations have been found between refractive index and density^{5,6}, surface tension^{7,8} and dielectric permittivity^{9,10} and also the use of refractive index to calculate the molecular composition of hydrogen bonded complexes¹¹. In recent past, several mixing rules^{5,12-18} have been used by several workers^{1,19-23} for the prediction of refractive indices of binary and multicomponent solutions from its density along with the values of refractive index and density of pure components.

In the present paper, the deviations in molar refraction, reduced free volume and refractive index along with the theoretically calculated values of refractive indices for eleven binary solutions viz. dimethylcarbonate (DMC) + methanol, DMC + cyclohexane, methanol + cyclohexane, methanol + benzene, DMC + benzene, *n*-hexane + α -pinene, *n*-hexane + β -pinene, *n*-hexane + *p*-

cymene, *n*-hexane + S(-)-limonene, *n*-hexane + 1,8-cineole, *n*-hexane + linalool and six ternary solutions viz. DMC + methanol + cyclohexane, DMC + methanol + benzene, DMC + methanol + ethanol, DMC + methanol + 1-propanol, *n*-hexane + cyclohexane + 1-butanol, benzene + cyclohexane + 2-methyl-2-butanol at 298.15 K are reported. Lorentz-Lorenz^{12,13}, Gladstone-Dale¹⁴, Wiener¹⁶, Heller⁵, Arago-Biot¹⁵, Eykman¹⁷ and Oster¹⁸ relations have been used for the theoretical predictions of refractive indices of all the solutions selected for the present study. The data required for this purpose have been collected from different sources²⁴⁻²⁹.

The non-electrolyte solutions selected for the present study are very important due to the versatile use of constituent liquid components of the solution. For example, DMC is considered an option for meeting the oxygenated specifications on gasoline, and as a means of converting natural gas to a liquid transportation fuel²⁴. α -Pinene is successfully used in asymmetric reduction for synthesizing optically pure materials with chiral organoboranes^{30,31}. Solution of methanol with benzene or cyclohexane is an azeotropic solution. For the engineering design of extractive rectification columns related to the industrial separation processes, the knowledge of the physical and derived properties of azeotropic solutions is required²⁶. The validity of above mentioned mixing rules for the predic-

tion of refractive indices of binary and ternary solutions is tested in terms of average percentage deviations (APD) of calculated values for the refractive index. As far as our knowledge is concerned, theoretical predictions of refractive indices, deviations in molar refraction and reduced free volume for the investigated systems have not been reported, so far.

Theoretical :

Fialkov and Fenerly³² and Fialkov³³ stated that the refractive index is an additive property of the pure components when the composition is expressed in volume fraction. Very recently Brocos *et al.*⁴ stated that the molar refraction deviation function must be calculated on a mole fraction basis and the refractive index deviation function on a volume fraction basis which makes it directly interpretable as a sign-reversed measure of the deviation of reduced free volume from ideality. Following their suggestions we have calculated the deviation in molar refraction, ΔR_m , of binary and ternary solutions using the expression

$$\Delta R_m = R_m - \sum_{i=1}^N x_i R_{m,i} \quad (1)$$

where R_m is the molar refraction of solution, and $R_{m,i}$ and x_i are the molar refraction and mole fraction of i -th component respectively. N is the number of components in solution.

The molar refraction was calculated using the Lorentz-Lorenz relation

$$R_m = \left(\frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 2} \right) V \quad (2)$$

where n and V are refractive index and molar volume respectively. Calculation of molar refraction deviation function on mole fraction basis implies the utility of a hard-sphere approximation in which all the excess volume is due to the deviation of free volume from ideality. Therefore, deviation of reduced free volume, $\Delta(V/R_m)$, is given by

$$\Delta \left(\frac{V}{R_m} \right) = \frac{n^2 + 2}{n^2 - 1} - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i V_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i R_{m,i}} \quad (3)$$

It is clear from eq. (3) that the deviation of reduced free volume can be calculated from measurements of refractive index of solution, n , and the properties of the pure

components without knowing the density of the solution.

The deviation in refractive index, Δn , is obtained from

$$\Delta n = n - \sum_{i=1}^N n_i \phi_i \quad (4)$$

where ϕ_i is the volume fraction of i -th component and is given by

$$\phi_i = \frac{x_i V_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i V_i} \quad (5)$$

Refractive index of solutions has been calculated by using various mixing rules^{5,12-18}.

Results and discussion

The values of density and refractive index of all the pure component liquids are taken from literature²⁴⁻²⁹ and collected in Table 1. The deviations in molar refraction, ΔR_m , reduced free volume, $\Delta(V/R_m)$, and refractive index, Δn , for binary solutions under the present investigation are calculated using eqs. (1), (3) and (4) respectively. Calculated values of ΔR_m , $\Delta(V/R_m)$ and Δn are plotted against the mole fraction of the first components for all the eleven binary liquid mixtures undertaken for the present investigation. The plots are shown graphically for some systems in Figs. 1-5. The refractive index of binary and ternary solutions has been calculated using

Table 1. Values of density (ρ) and refractive index (n) of pure liquids at 298.15 K

Liquids	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m ⁻³)	n	Refs.
DMC	1.06350	1.36640	27
Methanol	0.78660	1.32645	27
Cyclohexane	0.77380	1.42363	27
Benzene	0.87360	1.49729	26
α -Pinene	0.85390	1.46360	25
β -Pinene	0.86669	1.47610	25
<i>n</i> -Hexane	0.65486	1.37210	25
<i>p</i> -Cymene	0.85291	1.48820	25
S(-)-Limonene	0.83919	1.47050	25
1,8-Cineole	0.92011	1.45530	25
Linalool	0.85760	1.46050	25
Ethanol	0.78500	1.35922	24
1-Propanol	0.79950	1.38307	24
1-Butanol	0.80570	1.39717	28
2-Methyl-2-butanol	0.80450	1.40238	29

Fig. 1

Fig. 5

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Lorentz-Lorenz^{12,13}, Gladstone-Dale¹⁴, Wiener¹⁶, Heller⁵, Arago-Biot¹⁵, Eykman¹⁷ and Oster¹⁸ relations and results are discussed in terms of APD values for both the binary and ternary solutions. The results are displayed in Tables 2 and 3. Required data for this purpose have been taken from literature²⁴⁻²⁹.

As evident from Figs. 1-5, the values of ΔR_m are positive in all binary solutions in the entire composition range except for the binary solution (DMC + cyclohexane), where ΔR_m is negative at some mole fractions of DMC. Deviation in molar refraction is a measure of the strength of interaction between solute and solvent in solution. It is a sensitive function of wavelength, temperature and solution composition. The positive values of ΔR_m suggest the presence of weak interactions between components of solutions. According to Brocos *et al.*⁴, deviations in refractive index on volume fraction basis can be interpreted as a measure of intermolecular interactions. Deviations in refractive index for the binary solutions show similar trend, although with opposite sign, as shown by the corresponding excess molar volumes²⁷⁻²⁹.

Deviations in molar refraction, (ΔR_m), reduced free volume, $\Delta(V/R_m)$ and refractive index, Δn have also been theoretically calculated for six ternary solutions viz. DMC + methanol + cyclohexane, DMC + methanol + benzene, DMC + methanol + ethanol, DMC + methanol + 1-propanol, *n*-hexane + cyclohexane + 1-butanol and benzene + cyclohexane + 2-methyl-2-butanol at 298.15 K. The results of calculation show that ΔR_m has positive values in all ternary solutions investigated in the entire composition range except for two ternary solutions (DMC + methanol + cyclohexane and benzene + cyclohexane + 2-methyl-2-butanol), where ΔR_m is negative at some mole fractions. Positive values of ΔR_m suggest weak interactions between components of solutions. Further, it has been found that Δn have positive values for all ternary

Table 2. Average percentage deviations of calculated values of refractive index using Lorentz-Lorenz (L-L), Gladstone-Dael (G-D), Weiner (Wi), Heller (He), Arago-Biot (A-B), Eykman (Eyk) and Oster (Os) relations for binary solutions

Solution	L-L	G-D	Wi	He	A-B	Eyk	Os
DMC + methanol	0.034	0.029	0.031	0.035	0.029	0.016	0.013
DMC + benzene	-0.079	-0.149	-0.121	-0.067	-0.149	-0.051	-0.120
DMC + cyclohexane	-0.267	-0.278	-0.274	-0.262	-0.278	-0.029	-0.062
Methanol + cyclohexane	-0.085	-0.100	-0.094	-0.043	-0.100	-0.011	-0.031
Methanol + benzene	0.051	-0.063	-0.012	0.109	-0.063	-0.025	-0.124
<i>n</i> -Hexane + α -pinene	0.101	0.072	0.083	0.113	0.072	0.035	0.015
<i>n</i> -Hexane + β -pinene	0.150	0.108	0.125	0.159	0.108	0.055	0.025
<i>n</i> -Hexane + <i>p</i> -cymene	0.162	0.115	0.134	0.184	0.115	0.086	0.050
<i>n</i> -Hexane + S(-)-limonene	0.116	0.084	0.096	0.131	0.084	0.041	0.018
<i>n</i> -Hexane + 1,8-cineole	0.052	0.027	0.037	0.062	0.027	-0.014	-0.031
<i>n</i> -Hexane + linalool	0.077	0.047	0.059	0.081	0.047	0.056	0.030

Table 3. Average percentage deviations of calculated values of refractive index using Lorentz-Lorenz (L-L), Gladstone-Dael (G-D), Weiner (Wi), Heller (He), Arago-Biot (A-B), Eykman (Eyk) and Oster (Os) relations for ternary solutions

Solution	L-L	G-D	Wi	He	A-B	Eyk	Os
DMC + methanol + cyclohexane	-0.318	-0.348	-0.337	-1.711	-0.348	-0.041	-0.096
DMC + methanol + benzene	0.832	0.744	0.779	-0.232	0.744	-0.036	-0.133
DMC + methanol + ethanol	0.397	0.390	0.392	-0.164	0.390	0.009	0.003
DMC + methanol + 1-propanol	0.562	0.557	0.559	-0.170	0.557	0.008	-0.004
<i>n</i> -Hexane + cyclohexane + 1-butanol	-0.427	-0.440	-0.435	-0.101	-0.440	0.001	-0.013
Benzene + cyclohexane + 2-methyl-2-butanol	-0.449	-0.472	-0.466	-1.496	-0.472	-0.035	-0.084

solutions except the solutions DMC + methanol + cyclohexane, *n*-hexane + cyclohexane + 1-butanol and benzene + cyclohexane + 2-methyl-2-butanol), where Δn is negative in the entire composition range. Deviations in refractive index have opposite sign to the deviation of reduced free volume for many solutions under present investigation which support the physical significance of former. The exhaustive table containing the values of ΔR_m , $\Delta(V/R_m)$ and Δn for six ternary solutions has not been given. The interested persons can obtain this from authors.

A perusal of Table 2 reveals a close similarity in the predictions of refractive indices between Oster and Eykman relations, as well as between Arago-Biot and Gladstone-Dale relations. The best predictions of refractive indices for binary solutions are obtained with Eykman and Oster mixing rules.

As seen in Table 3, a close similarity in the predictions of refractive index values was observed between Oster and Eykman relations, as well as between Gladstone-Dale and Arago-Biot relations for all the ternary solutions investigated. The best predictions of refractive indices of ternary solutions are obtained with Eykman and Oster

mixing rules.

In conclusion we can say that Eykman and Oster relations are fit for the best predictions of refractive indices of binary and ternary solutions.

Acknowledgement

One of the author N. K. Soni is thankful to CSIR, New Delhi, for the financial support.

References

1. B. Giner, A. Villares, M. C. Lopez, F. M. Royo and C. Lafuente, *Phys. Chem. Liq.*, 2005, **43**, 13.
2. M. C. S. Subha, G. Narayana-Swamy, M. Eswari-Bai and K. S. V. Krishna Rao, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2004, **43**, 1876.
3. G. Savaroglu and E. Aral, *Fluid Phase Equilib.*, 2004, **215**, 253.
4. P. Brocos, A. Pineiro, R. Bravo and A. Amigo, *Phys. Chem. Chem.-Phys.*, 2003, **5**, 550
5. W. Heller, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, **69**, 1123.
6. J. R. Partington, "An Advanced Treatise on Physical Chemistry", Longmans and Green, London, 1953, Vol. 4.
7. I. L. Acevedo, G. C. Pedrosa and M. Katz, *An. Asoc. Quim. Argent.*, 1990, **78**, 161.

8. A. Pineiro, P. Brocos, A. Amigo, M. Pintos and R. Bravo, *Phys. Chem. Liq.*, 2000, **38**, 251.
9. H. Frohlich, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1948, **44**, 38.
10. J. Malecki and M. Dutkiewicz, *J. Sol. Chem.*, 1999, **28**, 101.
11. A. H. Buep and M. Baron, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1988, **92**, 840.
12. H. A. Lorentz, *Wied. Ann.*, 1880, **9**, 41.
13. L. Lorenz, *Wied. Ann.*, 1880, **1**, 70.
14. D. Dale and F. Gladstone, *Phylos. Trans. R. Soc. London*, 1864, **153**, 317.
15. D. F. J. Arago and J. B. Biot, *Mem. Acad. Fr.*, 1806, 7.
16. O. Wiener, *Leipzig. Ber.*, 1910, **62**, 256.
17. J. F. Eykman, *Rec. Trav. Chim. Pays. Bas. Belg.*, 1895, **14**, 185.
18. G. Oster, *Chem. Rev.*, 1948, **43**, 319.
19. T. M. Aminabhavi, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1984, **29**, 54.
20. J. D. Pandey, A. K. Shukla, R. K. Shukla and R. D. Rai, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, **29**, 336.
21. J. D. Pandey, A. K. Shukla, R. K. Shukla and R. D. Rai, *Phys. Chem. Liq.*, 1988, **18**, 337.
22. S. S. Bhatti, K. P. Prabhakar and D. P. Singh, *Indian J. Pure Appl. Phys.*, 1995, **33**, 18.
23. J. D. Pandey, V. Vyas, P. Jain, G. P. Dubey, N. Tripathi and R. Dey, *J. Mol. Liq.*, 1999, **81**, 123.
24. J. Canosa, A. Rodriguez and J. Tojo, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 2003, **35**, 2021.
25. F. Comelli, S. Ottani, R. Francesconi and C. Castellari, *J. Chem Eng. Data*, 2002, **47**, 93.
26. A. Rodriguez, J. Canosa and J. Tojo, *J. Chem Eng. Data*, 1999, **44**, 1298.
27. J. Canosa, A. Rodriguez and J. Tojo, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2001, **46**, 846.
28. E. Mascato, L. Mosteiro, M. M. Pineiro, J. Garcia, T. P. Iglesias and J. L. Legido, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 2001, **33**, 269.
29. M. Iglesias, M. M. Pineiro, G. Marino, B. Orge, M. Dominguez and J. Tojo, *Fluid Phase Equilib.*, 1999, **154**, 123.
30. C. H. Brown, M. Srebnik and P. V. Ramachandran, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1989, **54**, 1577.
31. C. H. Brown, J. Chandrasekharan and P. V. Ramachandran, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **110**, 1539.
32. Y. Y. Fialkov and G. N. Fenerly, *Russ. Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **9**, 1205.
33. Y. Y. Fialkov, *Russ. J. Phys. Chem.*, 1967, **41**, 398.